

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1940	Moniruzzaman	1961	1977	2005		Bangladeshi linguist (poetry, song lyrics, literary criticism and studies of folklore)	
1940	Richard Bauman	1963	1968	2009		American folklorist and anthropologist	
1940	Alessandra Melucco Vaccaro	1963		2000 w		Italian historian and archaeologist (the High Middle Ages, archaeological restoration, and environment and landscape)	1940-2000
1940	Javier de Hoz	1964	1966	2010		Spanish philologist (Paleohispanic languages, historical linguistics, ancient Celtic languages, history of writing, preclassical Greek literature, Greek epigraphy, and ancient Greek theatre)	1940-2019
1940	Ray C. Dougherty	1964	1968	2014		American linguist	
1940	Barbara Stoler Miller	1964	1966	1993 w		American scholar of Sanskrit literature	1940-1993
1940	Catherine S. Fowler	1964	1964	2008 w		American anthropologist whose work has focused on preserving the cultures of the native people of the Great Basin	
1940	Victoria Bricker	1964	1968	2015 w		American anthropologist and ethnographer, known for her studies of Mesoamerican culture	
1940	Robson Bonnicksen	1964	1974	2004		American anthropologist who undertook pioneering research in First American studies, popularized the field and founded the Center for the Study of Early Man at the University of Maine (Orono) in 1981	1940-2004
1940	Aleksander Szwedek	1965	1969			Polish linguist	
1940	Arnold Zwicky	1965	1965	2010		American linguist	
1940	Charles Perfetti	1965	1967	2014		American psycholinguist (cognitive science of language and reading processes)	
1940	David Rood	1965	1969	2014		American linguist	
1940	Herbert H Clark	1965	1966	2015		American Psycholinguist	
1940	Barbara H Partee	1965	1965	2004 w		American Linguistics and Philosophy	
1940	Martin Ferguson Smith	1963		1995		British scholar and writer	
1940	Asa Kasher	1966	1971			Israeli philosopher and linguist	
1940	Joan Solà Cortassa	1966	1970	2010		Spanish (Catalan) linguist and philologist	1940-2010
1940	Hartmut Steinecke	1966	1966	2005		German literary critic and university lecturer	1940-2020

1940	Stephen Thomas Knight	1966		2006	Australian distinguished research professor in English literature	1940-2011
1940	Joel E. Siegel	1966		1998	American professor of English and film studies at Georgetown University, a film and music critic, a music producer, and a lyricist	1940-2004
1940	Jane Tompkins	1966	1966	2011 w	American literary scholar who has worked on canon formation, feminist literary criticism, and reader response criticism	
1940	Keith H. Basso	1966	1967	2006	American cultural and linguistic anthropologist	1940-2013
1940	Sadegh Malek Shahmirzadi	1966	1977	2007	Iranian archaeologist and anthropologist	
1940	Miguel Barnet	1966	1996		Cuban writer, novelist and ethnographer	
1940	John Milfull	1966	1968	1996	Australian academic, educator and professor of German	1940-2016
1940	Averil Cameron	1966	1966	2010 w	British Professor of Late Antique and Byzantine History	
1940	Anya Peterson Royce	1967	1974	2002 w	American Chancellor's Professor of Anthropology and of Comparative Literature	
1940	David Woodley Packard	1967	1967	2002	American former professor (support for classical studies, especially the digitization of classics research)	
1940	Marina Tarlinskaja	1967	1967	2014 w	Russian-American linguist specializing in the statistical analysis of verse	
1940	Bruce Kapferer	1967	1969	2014	Australian anthropologist	
1940	Richard Bulliet	1967	1967	2015	American professor of history (history of Islamic society and institutions, the history of technology, and the history of the role of animals in human society)	
1940	Klaus Berger	1967	1967	2006	German Professor of New Testament Theology	1940-2020
1940	Wendy Doniger	1968	1968	2018	American the Mircea Eliade Distinguished Service Professor of the History of Religions	
1940	Elizabeth Wayland Barber	1968	1968	2007 w	American scholar and expert on archaeology, linguistics, textiles, and folk dance	
1940	Thomas Trautmann	1968	1968	2011	American historian, cultural anthropologist and Professor Emeritus of History and Anthropology	
1940	Esther Newton	1968	1968	2005 w	American cultural anthropologist best known for her pioneering work on the ethnography of lesbian and gay communities in the United States	

1940 James Joseph Fox	1968	1968	2006	American anthropologist and historian of Indonesia
1940 Louise Lamphere	1968	1968	2009 w	American anthropologist
1940 František Čermák	1969	1976	2005	Czech linguist
1940 John Grinde	1969	1971		American linguist, author, management consultant, trainer and co-founder of NLP internationally
1940 Robert Blust	1969	1974		American prominent linguist (historical linguistics, lexicography and ethnology)
1940 Mogens Herman Hansen	1969	1973	2010	Danish classical philologist and classical demographer(leading scholars in Athenian Democracy and the Polis)
1940 Richard Robbins	1969	1970	2008	American Distinguished Teaching Professor of anthropology
1940 Andrew Benjamin Gonzalez	1970	1970	2006	Filippino linguist, writer, educator, and a De La Salle Brother
1940 Philippe Barbaud	1970	1974	2005	Canadian linguist (Quebec)
1940 Болдырев Борис Васильевич	1970	1970		Russian philologist (Comparative descriptive morphology of the Tungus-Manchu languages, lexicography of the Evenki language and its dialects)
1940 John Irwin	1970	1970	2016	American poet and literary critic
1940 Wendy Rosalind James	1970	1970	2007 w	British social anthropologist and academic
1940 François Bizot	1970		2009	French anthropologist, the only Westerner to have survived imprisonment by the Khmer Rouge
1940 David Bindman	1970	1970	2005	British emeritus Durning-Lawrence professor of the history of art at University College London
1940 Adrian Hollis	1970		2007	British English classical scholar and correspondence chess grandmaster (title awarded in 1976)
1940 Roberto Magliola	1970	1970	2002	Italian-American academic specializing in European hermeneutics and deconstruction, in comparative philosophy, and in inter-religious dialogue
1940 Ali Mohammad Haghshenas	1971	1971	2004	Iranian linguist
1940 Jeffrey Mass	1971	1971	2001	American academic, historian, author and Japanologist
1940 Paul Marius Martin	1971	1971	2002	French Latinist and historian of ancient Rome
1940 Peter Macnair	1971		1997	Canadian Anthropologist

1940	S. Kent Brown	1971	1971	2010	American professor of ancient scripture and the director of ancient studies at Brigham Young University	
1940	Zoltán Abádi Nagy	1972	1979	2005 w	Hungarian Professor Emeritus of English, North American Department	
1940	Alice Davison	1972	1972	2016 w	American linguist	
1940	Robert Rodman	1972	1981	2017	American professor of computer science, computational linguist	
1940	Leroy Vail	1972	1972	1999	American specialist in African studies and educator (history and linguistics of Central Africa)	
1940	Nick Clements	1973	1973	2009	American theoretical linguist specializing in phonology	
1940	Rod Ellis	1974	1982	2016	British linguist (Kenneth W. Mildener Prize-winner)	
1940	Khurshid Rizvi	1974	1981	1995	Indian-Pakistani multifaceted scholar of oriental languages who possesses equal dexterity in Arabic, Persian, Urdu and English	
1940	Raoul J. Granqvist	1975	1975	2005	Swedish professor emeritus of English literature	
1940	Hollis Liverpool	1977	1993	2000	Trinidadian Professor of History, singer, lector on the history and culture of calypso music	
1940	Nancy Condee	1979	1979	w	American Professor of Slavic and Film Studies	
1940	Alfonsas Andriuškevičius	1982		2009	Lithuanian poet and art historian	
1940	Carol Delaney	1984	1984	2004 w	American anthropologist (anthropological sub-discipline of cultural anthropology, focusing on gender and religion)	
1941	Furio Jesi	1956	No	1980	Italian historian, writer, archaeologist, and philosopher	1941-1980
1941	Renato Rosaldo	1960	1971	2009	American cultural anthropologist	
1941	George Lakoff	1962	1966	2016	American cognitive linguist and philosopher	
1941	Andrew Pawley	1962	1986	2006	New Zealand linguist (Austronesian languages, Papuan languages, lexicography, phraseology)	
1941	Gian Biagio Conte	1962			Italian classicist and professor of Latin Literature	
1941	Carmel Schrire	1962	1968	2009 w	South African professor of anthropology	
1941	Herbert Kessler	1963	1965	2013	American medieval art historian active in the late twentieth and early twenty-first century	
1941	Ives Goddard	1964	1969	2012	American Linguistic Anthropologist	1941-2012

1941 David Crystal	1964	No	2015	British linguist (English language learning and teaching, clinical linguistics, forensic linguistics, language death, "ludic linguistics" (Crystal's neologism for the study of language play),[8] style, English genre, Shakespeare, indexing, and lexicography)	
1941 Norma Broude	1964	1967	2010 w	American art historian and scholar of feminism and 19th century French and Italian painting	
1941 John J. Ohala	1965	1969	2004	American Professor Emeritus in linguistics	
1941 Norman Fairclough	1965		2006	British linguist	
1941 Paul Kiparsky	1965	1965	2007	Finnish professor of linguistics at Stanford University	
1941 Wayles Browne	1965	1983	2016	British linguist, Slavist, translator and editor of Slavic journals	
1941 Sandra Thompson	1965	1969	2005 w	American linguist (discourse analysis, typology, and interactional linguistics)	
1941 Julia S. Falk	1965	1968	2006 w	American linguist	
1941 David H. Turner	1965		2006	Canadian professor of Anthropology	
1941 Rosalind E. Krauss	1965	1969	2014	American art critic, art theorist and a professor at Columbia University in New York City	
1941 Julia Penelope	1966	1971	2013	American linguist, critical thinkers on lesbian and feminist issues	1941-2013
1941 Eric Gans	1966	1966	2007	American literary scholar, philosopher of language, and cultural anthropologist	
1941 Monika Boehm-Tettelbach	1966	1975	2006 w	German Indologist (religious history and literature of northern India from the 16th century)	
1941 Adam Kuper	1966	1966	2006	South African anthropologist most closely linked to the school of social anthropology	
1941 Walt Wolfram	1967	1969	2006	American sociolinguist	
1941 Andrew Sihler	1967	1967	1999	American linguist (comparative linguistics, Indo-European languages)	
1941 Christopher Ehret	1967	1968		American scholar of African history and African historical linguistics	
1941 James Hurford	1967		2009	British-American linguist and academic	
1941 Alan Macfarlane	1967	1967	2007	British anthropologist and historian	
1941 Jean-Pierre Olivier de Sardan	1967	1967	2008	French- Nigerien anthropologist	

1941	E. N. Anderson	1967	1967	2006	American anthropologist (cultural anthropology, cultural ecology, ethnobiology, and food and nutrition in China, Pacific Northwest, and the Yucatan (Yucatec Maya))		
1941	Sajida Alvi	1967	1967	2010	w	Pakistani-Canadian historian of Islam in South Asia	
1941	Lauri Karttunen	1968	1969	2011		American Adjunct Professor in Linguistics	
1941	Roberta Frank	1968	1968	2019	w	American philologist (Old English and Old Norse language and literature)	
1941	Anne K. Mellor	1968	1968		w	American scholar in Romantic literature, British cultural history, feminist theory, philosophy, art history and gender studies	
1941	Asko Parpola	1968	1968	2004		Finnish Indologist and Sindhologist	
1941	Michael E. Moseley	1968	1968	2008		American anthropologist	
1941	Lawrence Rosen	1968	1968	2017		American cultural anthropologist who has authored and co-authored a number of works on medical, social, and cultural anthropology, with fieldwork in Melanesia (Manus), rural Mexico, and her mother's home town in Italy	
1941	Thomas P. Saine	1968	1968	2005		American professor of German studies	1941-2013
1941	Anncharlott Eschmann	1968	1969	1977	w	German scholar of religion	1941-1977
1941	Benjamin H. D. Buchloh	1969	1994	2004		German art historian, the Andrew W. Mellon Professor of Modern Art in the History of Art	
1941	Marilyn Strathern	1969	1969	2008	w	British anthropologist, who has worked largely with the Mount Hagen people of Papua New Guinea and dealt with issues in the UK of reproductive technologies	
1941	Richard K. Nelson	1969		2019		American cultural anthropologist and writer	1941-2019
1941	Carter V. Findley	1969	1969			American Humanities Distinguished Professor in the History Department	
1941	Dianne Sachko Macleod	1970	1981	2007	w	American Professor Emerita 19th-Century Visual Culture Modern & Gender Studies	
1941	Walter D. Mignolo	1970	1974			Argentine semiotician and the William H. Wannamaker Professor of Literature	
1941	Paul S. Cohen	1970	No	2007		American linguist (for IBM in such areas as automatic speech recognition, text-to-speech, and natural language processing)	

1941	Sherry Ortner	1970	1970	2004 w	American cultural anthropologist and Distinguished Professor of Anthropology
1941	Daniel Bates	1970	1970	2008	American professor of anthropology, the editor-in-chief of Human Ecology
1941	Richard Price	1970	1970	2011	American anthropologist and historian, best known for his studies of the Caribbean and his experiments with writing ethnography
1941	Helga W. Kraft	1970	1970	2010 w	German-American Professor of Germanic Studies
1941	Lia Schwartz	1971	1971	2016 w	Argentine-American historian of Spanish and comparative literature
1941	Lise Menn	1971	1975	2008 w	American linguist (psycholinguistics)
1941	Richard Schmidt	1971	1974	2012	American linguist
1941	K. M. Petyt	1971	1971	2019	British sociolinguist and historian
1941	Calvin Veltman	1971	1983	2014	American sociologist, demographer and sociolinguist
1941	Detlev Blanke	1971	1976	2016	German Esperantist
1941	Martin Hinds	1971		1988	British scholar of the Middle East and historiographer of early Islamic history
1941	Donald Cole	1971	1971	2007	American noted anthropologist at the American University in Cairo
1941	H. James Birx	1971	1971	2008	American anthropologist
1941	Deirdre Wilson	1972	1974	2008 w	British linguist and cognitive scientist
1941	Stephen Krashen	1972	1972	2016	American Linguist, educational researcher
1941	Robert Thurman	1972	1972	1988	American Buddhist author and academic who has written, edited, and translated several books on Tibetan Buddhism
1941	Fadwa El Guindi	1972	1972	2010 w	Egyptian-American anthropologist and former professor of anthropology
1941	Beatriz Góis Dantas	1972		2006 w	Brazilian anthropologist, folklorist, sociologist, writer, and professor
1941	Barend Jan Terwiel	1972	1972	2006	Dutch-Australian anthropologist, historian and an expert on Thailand
1941	Carroll D. Osburn	1972	1974	2004	American scholar recognized as one of North America's leading New Testament textual critics and a prominent Christian egalitarian

1941	Jerold A. Edmondson	1973	1973	2011	American linguist (historical and comparative linguistics, Asian linguistics, field linguistics, and phonetics)	
1941	Françoise Ozanne-Rivierre	1973	1973	2006 w	French linguist	
1941	Bonnie McCay	1974	1976	2015 w	American anthropologist and Board of Governors Distinguished Service Professor Emerita at Rutgers University	
1941	Daniel E. Moerman	1974	1974	2006	American medical anthropologist and ethnobotanist, and an emeritus professor of anthropology	
1941	Leslie Desmangles	1975	1975	2003	Haitian professor of religion and international studies	
1941	Annie Zaenen	1976	1980	2011 w	American linguist	
1941	Karla Poewe	1976	1983	2004 w	German-Canadian anthropologist and historian	
1941	A. Graeme Auld	1976	1976	2007	British Old Testament scholar	
1941	Leanne Hinton	1978		w	American emerita professor of linguistics (American Indian languages, sociolinguistics, and language revitalization)	
1941	R. G. Tiedemann	1978		2006	German-American historian of Christianity in China	
1941	Marie-Lucie Tarpent	1982	1987	2007 w	Canadian linguist (Nisga'a language)	
1942	Jay Jasanoff	1963	1968	2008	American linguist	
1942	Francisco Rico Manrique	1964	1968		Spanish professor of Medieval Spanish Literature	
1942	Tilman Nagel	1964	1967	2008	German Orientalist	
1942	Elizabeth Webby	1965	1971	2007 w	Australian literary critic, editor and scholar in the field of literature	
1942	Robin Lakoff	1965	1967	2010 w	American sociolinguist (language and gender)	
1942	Darrell Tryon	1965	1965	2007	New Zealand linguist, academic, and specialist in Austronesian languages	1942-2013
1942	Ronald Langacker	1966	1966	2003	American linguist	
1942	Udo Fries	1966	1966	2007	Swiss Professor of English Linguistics	
1942	Jürgen Hein	1966	1968	2007	German literary critic	1942-2014
1942	Hermann Hunger	1966	1966	2007	Austrian Assyriologist, Professor of Assyriology	
1942	Conrad Phillip Kottak	1966	1966	2017	American anthropologist	
1942	Hoyt Alverson	1967	1968	2011	American Professor Emeritus of Anthropology	
1942	Vladimir Goss	1967	1972	2007	Croatian researcher medieval art (pre-Romanesque and Romanesque times, medieval cities in Croatia and Renaissance sculpture in Dalmatia)	

1942	Bernard Bernier	1967	1970	2014	Canadian anthropologist	
1942	Geneviève Hasenohr	1967		2002	French philologist and prolific scholar of medieval and Renaissance French literature	
1942	Heinz Halm	1967	1967	2008	German scholar of Islamic Studies, with a particular expertise on early Shia history, the Ismailites and other Shia sects	
1942	Dan Sperber	1968		2008	French social and cognitive scientist (cognitive anthropology and linguistic pragmatics)	
1942	Eve V. Clark	1968	1969	2017 w	American Linguist	
1942	John Onians	1968	1968	2007	British Professor Emeritus of World Art	
1942	Malcolm Ross	1968	1986	2008	Australian linguist (Austronesian languages, Papuan languages, historical linguistics, language contact)	
1942	Molefi K. Asante	1968	1968	2004	African-American professor and philosopher (African-American studies, African studies and communication studies)	
1942	Lyle Campbell	1968	1971		American scholar and linguist (Historical linguistics, Native American languages)	
1942	David R. Knechtges	1968	1968	2014	American sinologist, professor emeritus of Chinese literature	
1942	Joel Sherzer	1968	1968	2019	American anthropological linguist	
1942	Jonathan Kaye	1968	1970	2014	American linguist	
1942	Frances Esther Karttunen	1968	1970	2000 w	American academic linguist, historian and author	
1942	Pat Caplan	1968	1968	2003 w	British anthropologist and academic	
1942	Meave Leakey	1968	1968	2007 w	British palaeoanthropologist	
1942	Walther von Hahn	1968	1968	2007	German linguist and computer scientist	
1942	Vasim Mammadaliyev	1968	1968	2019	Azerbaijani scientist of oriental studies, dean of theology	1942-2019
1942	Daniel H. Bays	1968	1971	2012	American historian of China, best known for his works on Christianity in China	1942-2019
1942	Nancy H. Ramage	1969	1969	2007 w	American the Charles A. Dana Professor of the Humanities and Arts emerita	
1942	Roland Posner	1969	1972	2010	German semiotician	
1942	Karen McCarthy Brown	1969	1976	2009 w	American anthropologist specializing in the anthropology of religion	1942-2015

1942	Nicholas Williams	1970	1971		British-Irish celtologist, expert (Cornish language, Irish language, Manx language, phonology) and poet
1942	Melissa Bowerman	1970	1971	2007 w	American leading researcher in the area of language acquisition
1942	Janet Dean Fodor	1970	1970	w	American linguist (psycholinguistics, human sentence processing, prosody, learnability theory and L1 (first-language) acquisition)
1942	Barry Bruce Powell	1970	1970		American classical scholar
1942	Joan Halifax	1970		2009 w	American Zen Buddhist teacher, anthropologist, ecologist, civil rights activist, hospice caregiver, and the author
1942	William Divale	1970	1974	2009	American professor of anthropology
1942	Davydd Greenwood	1970	1973	2014	American the Goldwin Smith Professor of Anthropology and Director of the Institute for European Studies at Cornell University
1942	Ian Maddieson	1971	1977	2006	American phonetist
1942	Sandra Chung	1971	1976	2017 w	American linguist (Austronesian languages and syntax)
1942	Gideon Toury	1971	1977	2016	Israeli translation scholar and professor of Poetics, Comparative Literature and Translation Studies
1942	Michael Lapidge	1971	1971	2004	Canadian scholar in the field of Medieval Latin literature, particularly that composed in Anglo-Saxon England during the period 600–1100 AD
1942	Luisa Accati	1971		2009 w	Italian historian, anthropologist and feminist public intellectual
1942	Hebe Vessuri	1971		2010 w	Argentinean social anthropologist
1942	Dale F. Eickelman	1971	1971	2010	American anthropologist with an expertise on Middle East
1942	André Lemaire	1971		2002	French epigrapher, historian and philologist
1942	J. Gordon Melton	1971	1975		American religious scholar who was the founding director of the Institute for the Study of American Religion
1942	Cathrine Fabricius-Hansen	1972	1987	2012	Danish-Norwegian Germanist
1942	Jerzy Treder	1972	1973	2015	Polish philologist and linguist (Kashubian studies)

1942 Carol A. Breckenridge	1972	1976	2008 w	American anthropologist and Associate Professor of History
1942 Larry Shinn	1972	1972	2012	American Vice-President of Academic Affairs, Dean of Humanities and Head of the Religious Studies Department
1942 Jan Hjärpe	1972	1972		Swedish Islamicist and a professor emeritus in Islamic studies at the Centre for Theology and Religious Studies
1942 Elżbieta Tabakowska	1973		w	Polish linguist (cognitive linguistics and theory of translation)
1942 Peter E. Hook	1973	1973	2007	American professor emeritus in the Department of Asian Languages and Cultures
1942 Marcel Hénaff	1973	1980	2012	French philosopher and anthropologist
1942 Raymond C. Kelly	1973	1974	2002	American cultural anthropologist and ethnologist who has written on the origin of warfare, and on the basis of social inequality in human societies
1942 Donald Symons	1973	1978	2013	American anthropologist best known as one of the founders of evolutionary psychology, and for pioneering the study of human sexuality from an evolutionary perspective
1942 C. Wilfred Griggs	1973	1978	1991	American professor of ancient scripture
1942 Craig Mishler	1974	1981	2015	American Affiliate Research Professor at the Alaska Native Language Center (cultural anthropology, folklore, ethnomusicology)
1942 Jeanette Gundel	1974	1974	2012 w	American linguist (information structure and pragmatics)
1942 Jerry Hobbs	1974	1974	2013	American researcher in computational linguistics, discourse analysis, syntax, semantics
1942 Alba Zaluar	1974	1984	2008 w	Brazilian anthropologist, with emphases in urban anthropology[1] and in anthropology of violence
1942 Michael Lattke	1974	1974	2007	German scholar of the New Testament and early Christianity
1942 Sidra DeKoven Ezrahi	1975	1976	2011 w	Israeli Professor Emerita of Comparative Literature
1942 Kenneth Good	1975	1975	2013	American anthropologist most noted for his work among the Yanomami

1942 Helene P. Foley	1975	1975	2013 w	American classical scholar	
1942 Jenny Strauss Clay	1975		2018 w	American the William R. Kenan, Jr. Professor of Classics at the University of Virginia	
1942 Philippe Jacquin	1976		2002	French anthropologist	
1942 Donald Rayfield	1976	1978	2005	British English academic and Emeritus Professor of Russian and Georgian	
1942 Wulf Oesterreicher	1977	1977	2015	German Romanist, Hispanist, linguist and university professor	
1942 Penelope Eckert	1978	1978	w	American professor of linguistics (sociolinguistics, language and gender)	
1942 Gary O. Rollefson	1978	1978	2013	American Anthropologist	
1942 Harald Bjorvand	1978	1988	2009	Norwegian linguist	
1942 Yoram Bilu	1979	1979	2010	Israelt professor of anthropology and psychology	
1942 Signe Howell	1980	1980	2012 w	Norwegian social anthropologist	
1942 Ann Dunham	1982	1992	1995 w	American anthropologist (the economic anthropology and rural development of Indonesia), mother of Barack Obama	1942-1995
1942 Thomas Buckley	1982	1982	2015	American anthropologist and Buddhist monastic best known for his long-term ethnographic research with the Yurok Indians of northern California	1942-2015
1942 Chris Knight	1985	1987	2009	British anthropologist and political activist	
1943 Suad Joseph	1964	1975	2012 w	Lebanese Professor of Anthropology and Women and Gender Studies	
1943 Gerard Kempen	1965	1970	2011	Dutch Psycholinguist	
1943 Gillian Sankoff	1965	1968	2008 w	Canadian-American sociolinguist	
1943 Jeff Todd Titon	1966	1971	2013	American Professor of Music, Emeritus	
1943 Gary Witherspoon	1966	1966	2010	American professor of Native American studies	
1943 Sally Price	1966	1982	2011 w	American anthropologist, best known for her studies of so-called "primitive art" and its place in the imaginaire of Western viewers	
1943 Alan C. Swedlund	1966	1970	2018	American biological anthropologist	
1943 Stephen R. Anderson	1967	1969	2017	American linguist (morphology and history of linguistics)	
1943 Frederick Turner	1967	1967	2008	British-American poet, Professor of Literature and Creative Writing	

1943	Ronald Daus	1967	1967	2008	German Professor of Romance philology and cultural studies	
1943	Matt Cartmill	1967	1970	2008	American anthropologist and professor of anthropology in the College of Arts and Sciences	
1943	Ádám Anderle	1967	1967	2013	Hungarian historian, hispanist, full (university) professor	1943-2016
1943	Jules Lubbock	1968		2014	American professor of art history	
1943	Teun A. van Dijk	1968		2014	Dutch linguist	
1943	Sandra Cypess	1968	1968	2007 w	American Professor Emerita of Latin American Literature	
1943	Richard Lobban	1968	1973	2009	American anthropologist and early pioneer in social network modeling, archaeologist, Egyptologist, and Sudanist, foreign policy expert, human rights activist, mentor, father, and beekeeper	
1943	Robert S. Newman	1968	1972	2013	American anthropologist primarily known for his contribution to studying post-1961 Goa, India	
1943	H. Martin Wobst	1968	1971	2010	German-American anthropologist	
1943	Frank-Rutger Hausmann	1968	1968	2006	German Romanist and historian	
1943	Gerd Theissen	1968	1968	2009	German Protestant theologian and New Testament scholar	
1943	Caroline Humphrey	1969	1973	2010 w	British anthropologist	
1943	Malcolm Coulthard	1969	1970	2018	British expert witness in forensic linguistics	
1943	Thomas Elsaesser	1969	1971	2008	Dutch international film historian and professor of Film and Television Studies	1943-2019
1943	H. C. Wolfart	1969	1969	2008	German-Canadian researcher, editor, translator and Distinguished Professor of Linguistics	
1943	Francesco Remotti	1969		2009	Italian anthropologist	
1943	Hans Peter Duerr	1969	1971	1999	German anthropologist	
1943	Regna Darnell	1969	1969	2009 w	Canadian anthropologist and professor of Anthropology and First Nations Studies	
1943	Penelope Reed Doob	1969	1969	2014 w	American-Canadian medievalist, dance scholar, and medical researcher	1943-2017
1943	Elisabeth Piirainen	1970	1970	2008 w	German linguist and philologist	

1943	Harvey Sussman	1970	1970	2013	American linguist (speech production, speech perception, language and the brain, and neurolinguistics)
1943	Tracy D. Terrell	1970		1989	American education theorist (natural approach is a comprehension-based language learning methodology)
1943	Nina Auerbach	1970	1970	2009	American the John Welsh Centennial Professor of English Emerita
1943	Philip Furia	1970	1970	2011	American author and English literature professor
1943	Wulf Schiefenhövel	1970	1970	2008	German Medical doctor, anthropologist and human ethologist
1943	William Wyvill Fitzhugh IV	1970	1970	2017	American archaeologist and anthropologist who directs the Smithsonian's Arctic Studies Center and is a Senior Scientist at the National Museum of Natural History
1943	Colin William MacLeod	1970		1981	British Scottish classical scholar, educator and author
1943	Keith Allan	1971	1978	2011	Australian linguist
1943	Keith Rayner	1971	1974	2008	British cognitive psychologist (pioneering modern eye-tracking methodology in reading and visual perception)
1943	Peter Trudgill	1971	1971	2015	British linguist (sociolinguistics, English language, dialectology) and writer
1943	Michael Witzel	1971	1972		German-American philologist, comparative mythologist and Indologist
1943	Tom Conley	1971	1971		American philologist, Lowell Professor in the Departments of Romance Languages and Visual and Environmental Studies
1943	Catherine Ringen	1971	1975	2015 w	American phonologist
1943	A. Ronald Walton	1971	1971	1996	American professor of Chinese language and linguistics
1943	Maria Dolores	1971	1984	2008 w	Spanish philologist, historian, and university professor specializing in the Muslim world
1943	Carol R. Ember	1971	1971	2016 w	American cultural anthropologist, cross-cultural researcher and a writer
1943	Esther Pasztory	1971	1971	2013 w	American professor emerita of Pre-Columbian art history

1943	Mark Nathan Cohen	1971	1971	2010	American anthropologist (human evolution and demographic history, cultural evolution, biology, medical care and forensic anthropology)
1943	Inez De Florio-Hansen	1971	1971	2008 w	German applied linguist and educational psychologist whose work focuses on science-oriented teaching and learning with particular reference to multilingualism and intercultural competence
1943	Orvar Löfgren	1972	1978	2008 w	Swedish professor emeritus of ethnology
1943	Brian Street	1972		2010	British professor of language education at King's College London
1943	Paul Michael Lützeler	1972	1972	2020	German-American scholar of German studies and comparative literature
1943	Angelika Neuwirth	1972	1972	2011 w	German professor of Quranic studies
1943	Jyotindra Jain	1972	1972	2019	Indian art and cultural historian, and museologist
1943	Pierre Vernet	1973	1984	2010	Haitian linguist and lexicographer
1943	Peter John Roach	1973	1978	2004	British phonetician
1943	Denis Creissels	1973		2008	French professor of linguistics
1943	Angelika Kratzer	1973	1979	2018 w	German-American linguist
1943	Robert E. Hegel	1973	1973	2018	American sinologist specializing in the fiction of late imperial China
1943	Jeanne Guillemin	1973	1973	2005 w	American medical anthropologist and author
1943	Stephen C. Headley	1973	1979	2010	American social anthropologist and a priest of the Orthodox Church
1943	Dennis B. McGilvray	1973	1974	2017	American professor in the Department of Anthropology
1943	T. J. Clark	1973	1973	2010	British art historian and writer
1943	Christopher Green	1973	1973	2008	British art historian
1943	William A. Graham	1973	1973		American scholar of Islamic studies and the history of religion, the Murray A. Albertson Professor of Middle Eastern Studies
1943	Donald L. Rubin	1974	1978	2013	American linguist and sociolinguist
1943	Anders Piltz	1974	1977		Swedish latinist and medievalist, a priest in the Roman Catholic church and member of the Dominican Order
1943	Barbara Abbott	1974	1976	2006 w	American linguist
1943	Karl-Olov Arnstberg	1974	1977	2008	Swedish ethnologist and writer

1943	Jan Terje Faarlund	1974		2013	Norwegian linguist and professor emeritus of North Germanic languages	
1943	Donald Johanson	1974	1974		American paleoanthropologist (the fossil of a female hominin australopithecine known as "Lucy")	
1943	Riall Nolan	1974	1986	2014	American anthropologist	
1943	Joseph Skerrett	1975	1975	2009	American literary critic and professor of English	
1943	Diane Bell	1975	1981	2005 w	Australian feminist anthropologist, author and activist	
1943	Eduardo P. Archetti	1975	1976	2005	Argentinean anthropologist and sociologist, essayist and educator, considered one of the most original social scientists in Latin America	
1943	Martin Pickford	1975	1975	2013	British Chair in Paleoanthropology and Prehistory at the Collège de France	
1943	Tanya Reinhart	1975	1976	2005 w	Israeli linguist who wrote frequently on the Israeli-Palestinian conflict	
1943	Azizah Y. al-Hibri	1975	1975	2012 w	American philosopher and legal scholar who specializes in Islam and law	
1943	Irving Hexham	1975	1975	2008	British-Canadian Professor of Religious Studies	
1943	Pierre Chuvin	1976	1983	2011	French hellenist and historian	
1943	Mari Lyn Salvador	1976	1976	2015 w	American anthropologist, known for her work on Panamanian molas, worn by Kuna women	
1943	Fred Hardy	1977	1983	2004	German Professor of Indian Religions	
1943	Charles Goodwin	1977	1977	2017	American UCLA distinguished research professor of communication and key member of UCLA's Center for Language, Interaction and Culture	
1943	Oliver Taplin	1977	1977	2008	British academic and classicist	
1943	John A. Holm	1978	1978	2014	American linguist	
1943	T. Jack Thompson	1980	1980	2008	Irish mission historian and scholar of African Christianity	1943-2017
1943	Nasr Abu Zayd	1981	1981	2004	Egyptian Qur'anic thinker, author, academic and one of the leading liberal theologians in Islam	1943-2010
1943	Pan Wuyun	1982	1982		Chinese linguist and specialist in historical Chinese phonology	
1943	Deborah Fouts	1984	No	2011 w	American co-director of the Chimpanzee and Human Communication Institute (CHCI)	

1943	Jerome Branche	1995	1996		Guyanese American Professor of Latin American Literature and Cultural Studies in the Department of Hispanic Languages and Literatures	
1943	Jonathan Fox	1995	1997		Israeli the Yehuda Avner Professor of Religion and Politics	
1944	Robert G. Bednarik	1965			Austrian-Australian prehistorian and cognitive archeologist	
1944	Jonathan Culler	1967	1972	2019	American the Class of 1916 Professor of English and Comparative Literature	
1944	David Evans	1967	1976	2013	American ethnomusicologist and director of the Ethnomusicology/Regional Studies program at the Rudi E. Scheidt School of Music in the University of Memphis	
1944	Clémentine Nzuji	1968		2003 w	Democratic Republic of the Congo poet and writer (Bantu linguistics and oral literature)	
1944	Reinhard Brey Mayer	1968	No	2017	German philologist, researcher into pietism and specialist on the history of rhetoric	1944-2017
1944	Sheila Blumstein	1968	1970	2010 w	American professor emerita of cognitive, linguistic and psychological sciences	
1944	Georgia M. Green	1968	1971	2015 w	American linguist and academic	
1944	Victor Raskin	1968	1970	2014	Russian-American distinguished professor of linguistics	
1944	Richard S Kayne	1969	1969	2017	American linguist	
1944	Violeta Demonte	1969	1975	2007 w	Argentinean linguist chomskyana	
1944	Frederick Newmeyer	1969	1969	2003	American linguist (syntax, origin of language)	
1944	Jeremy Sabloff	1969	1969	2015	American anthropologist	
1944	Bruce Tomblin	1970	1970	2013	American language and communication scientist	
1944	James Rubin	1970	1972	2011	American Professor Nineteenth Century European Art History, Theory and Criticism, Art and Politics, Art and Philosophy	
1944	Richard M. Hogg	1970	1975	2007	British linguist (phonology, historical linguistics)	
1944	Jean-Marie Klinkenberg	1970	1971	2015	Belgian linguist and semiotician	
1944	Ellen Prince	1970	1974	2005 w	American linguist (pragmatics)	
1944	Hunter R. Rawlings III	1970	1970	2016	American classics scholar (philologist) and academic administrator	
1944	Elisabeth Croll	1970	1977	2006 w	New Zealander anthropologist	

1944	Jorun Solheim	1970	1970	2011 w	Norwegian social anthropologist and women's studies academic, whose work is centered on gender, culture and modernity
1944	Maxine Margolis	1970	1970	2012 w	American anthropologist and an inductee of the American Academy of Arts and Sciences
1944	Jerome H. Barkow	1970	1971	2006	Canadian anthropologist at Dalhousie University who has made important contributions to the field of evolutionary psychology
1944	Paul Rabinow	1970	1970	2019	American Professor of Anthropology at the University of California (Berkeley), Director of the Anthropology of the Contemporary Research Collaboratory (ARC), and former Director of Human Practices for the Synthetic Biology Engineering Research Center (SynBERC)
1944	Ruth Kempson	1971	1975	2011 w	British linguist (author Semantic Theory)
1944	Peter Bayley	1971	1971	2011	British scholar of French literature (specialising in 17th-century French literature), sermons and essays
1944	Else Mundal	1971	1971	2014 w	Norwegian philologist
1944	Rolandas Pavilionis	1971	1971	2000	Lithuanian philosopher, politician and Member of the European Parliament (MEP) for the Liberal Democratic Party
1944	Emily Martin	1971	1971	2018 w	American sinologist, anthropologist, and feminist
1944	Rupert Moser	1971	1971	2018	Swiss professor emeritus for social anthropology and African studies
1944	Henry Harpending	1971	1972	2016	American anthropologist
1944	David M. Rosen	1971	1973	2009	American anthropologist
1944	Michelle Rosaldo	1971	1972	1981	American social, linguistic, and psychological anthropologist, pioneering role in women's studies and the anthropology of gender
1944	Anna Lomax Wood	1971	1991	w	American anthropologist and public folklorist
1944	Eric Reuland	1972	1979	2011	Dutch linguist
1944	Geoffrey Huck	1972	1984	2018	Canadian linguist (English, Writing, Classics)
1944	Koenraad Kuiper	1972	1972	2011	New Zealand linguist
1944	Peter J. Rabinowitz	1972	1972	2019	American professor of comparative literature
1944	Brent Galloway	1972	1977	2008	American linguist (Amerindian languages), composer of classical music

1944	John Rahn	1972	1974	2013	American Professor of Music
1944	Elinor Ochs	1972	1974	2015 w	American linguistic anthropologist, and Distinguished Professor of Anthropology
1944	Fernando Coronil	1972	1987	2009	Venezuelan anthropologist best known for his study of the politics of oil in Venezuela
1944	Gregor Schoeler	1972	1978	2009	German contemporary non-Muslim Islamic scholar
1944	Gisela Hellenkemper Salies	1972	1972	1999 w	German classical archaeologist and museum curator
1944	Dafydd Gibbon	1973	1975	2009	British emeritus professor of English and General Linguistics
1944	Robert L. Caserio	1973	1973	2015	American Professor Emeritus of English, Comparative Literature, and Women's, Gender, and Sexuality Studies
1944	Merritt Ruhlen	1973	1973	2011	American linguist, lecturer in Anthropological Sciences and Human Biology
1944	Adolfo Elizaincín	1973		2006	Uruguayan scholar and linguist
1944	Christoph Wulf	1973	1973	2009	German academic, professor of anthropology and education
1944	Robert Hugh Layton	1973	1973	2012	British anthropologist and Fellow of the British Academy
1944	Richard M. Moyle	1973		2009	New Zealand academic specialising in ethnomusicology of the Pacific and Australia
1944	Margaret B. Blackman	1973	1973	w	American anthropologist (human evolution and demographic history, cultural evolution, biology, medical care and forensic anthropology)
1944	Judith Friedlander	1973	1973	2017 w	American anthropologist
1944	Hartmut Traunmüller	1974	1983	2011	Swedish Professor emeritus of phonetics
1944	Jens Elmegård Rasmussen	1974	1989	2009	Norwegian expert on Proto-Indo-European and Indo-European languages, history of Eskimo–Aleut languages and linguistic diachrony
1944	James Kari	1974	1974	1997	American linguist
1944	Paul Nation	1974		2013	American-New Zealander leading language teaching methodology and vocabulary acquisition linguist researcher, mainly for English as a foreign language

1944	Dean Falk	1974	1976	2014 w	American academic Neuroanthropologist who specializes in the evolution of the brain and cognition in higher primates
1944	Janet D. Spector	1974		1995 w	American archaeologist (archaeology of gender and ethnoarchaeology)
1944	Nina Felshin	1974		2009 w	American curator, writer, art historian and activist
1944	Jerome Silbergeld	1974	1974	2016	American scholar of Chinese art history
1944	Kristen Hawkes	1975	1976	2011 w	American anthropologist (human evolution and sociobiology, author of the “grandmother hypothesis”)
1944	Margaretta M. Lovell	1975	1980	2010 w	American the Jay D. McEvoy Professor of the History of Art
1944	Letas Palmaitis	1975	1975	2007	Lithuanian linguist and public figure, propagandist of the Prussian language revival
1944	Hartmut Zinser	1975	1975	2009	German scholar in the field of religious studies, history of religions, and ethnology
1944	Shelly Errington	1975	1978	2009 w	American cultural anthropologist specializing in the studies of plastic art and narrative arts, focusing on documentary film, photography, arts, and multi-media
1944	Jean-Pierre Mahé	1975		2018	French orientalist, philologist and historian of Caucasus, specialist of Armenian studies
1944	Andrew T. Lincoln	1975	1975	2013	British New Testament scholar
1944	Øivind Andersen	1976	1976	2014	Norwegian philologist
1944	Aud Talle	1976	1988	2011 w	Norwegian social anthropologist
1944	Unni Wikan	1976	1980	2013 w	Norwegian professor of social anthropology
1944	André Włodarczyk	1977	1977	2011	Polish-French japanologist and linguist
1944	Solomon Momyenyé	1977	1986	2006	Kenyan Professor of Philosophy and Religious Studies
1944	Valentyna Kuzyk	1978		w	Ukrainian Musicologist (Музикознавство, Теорія Музики, Критика)
1944	Penelope Brown	1978	1979	2018 w	American anthropological linguist
1944	Heleen Sancisi-Weerdenburg	1978	1980	2000 w	Dutch ancient historian, specializing in classical Greek and Achaemenid history
1944	Synnøve des Bouvrie	1978	1988	2014 w	Norwegian Professor emérита, Greek and Latin, ancient culture
1944	Larry Trask	1979	1984	2004	American-British linguist (Basque language, historical linguistics, origin of language)

1944	Alain Desreumaux	1979	1979	2010	French historian of religion, specializing on Syrian and Aramaic christo-palestinian communities	
1944	Viorel Munteanu	1980	2001		Romanian composer, musicologist, and lecturer	
1944	Rod Ellis	1980		2016	British linguist (Second language acquisition)	
1944	Gary Russell Libby	1980		2002	American art historian, author, educator and former museum director known for his books and scholarly exhibitions in the visual arts and his work on the history and development of the Florida School of Art	
1944	Michael Ann Holly	1981	1981	2016 w	American art historian (historiography, theory of art history)	
1944	Beata Agrell	1981	1983	2011 w	Swedish Professor emerita of Comparative Literature	
1944	Paul Frommer	1981	1981	2011	American communications professor, linguistics consultant (John Carter (2012), Avatar (2009) and Conlanging: The Art of Crafting Tongues (2017))	
1944	Edna Ahgeak MacLean	1981	1995	2014 w	American Iñupiaq (Alaska Native) academic administrator, linguist, anthropologist and educator	
1944	Jane Dammen McAuliffe	1981	1984	w	American educator, internationally known scholar of Islam and the inaugural Director of National and International Outreach at the Library of Congress	
1944	Florinda Donner	1982	No	1998 w	American writer and anthropologist known as one of Carlos Castaneda's "witches" (the term for three women who were friends of Castaneda)	1944-1998
1944	Denny Moore	1984	1984	w	American linguist and anthropologist	
1944	Karma Lekshe Tsomo	1987	2000	2012 w	American Buddhist nun and Professor of Religious Studies	
1944	Gillian Wigglesworth	1988	1993	2016 w	Australian linguist	
1944	Alain le Pichon	1988		2009	French Anthropologist and President of Transcultural's international institute	
1944	Pnina Werbner	1989		2010 w	British social anthropologist	